

Review on Adult Learning Theory and Approach

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Abstract

The theory of adult learning and teaching uses skill as a merging perception to relate gaining of knowledge, skills, and attitudes to improved performance. This theory encourages much adult learning as it is a part of constant learning theory that takes place for a lifetime. Adult learning is a lifetime practice whereby knowledge is designed through the transformation of adults' knowledge. The more adult are familiar with this knowledge base, the more effective their training can be, and the more approachable their practice can be to the needs of adult learners. This article presents the theoretical review on adult learning theory and approach in educational perspective.

Introduction

First and foremost, adult education is an integral portion of everyday life and is perceived as a process of changing life experience into knowledge and skills, so it looks like a simple phenomenon at first glance (Kim & Merriam, 2010; Illeris, 2010). Early studies defined adult education as a lifelong process in which knowledge is produced through the transformation of experience (Illeris, 2010; Kolb, 1984). However, because there are no definitions, models, or theories that explain how adults learn, why they learn, how best to assist the learning process, and why adults participate in the learning process. It is also described as a complex process (Merriam, 2010). Boeren, (2017). In addition, adult education in Meliam (2010) tends to be a very independent and independent process. Self-study is a difficult occurrence that involves a variety of activities, decision-making tactics, knowledge experiences, and a certain level of accountability to achieve education goals (Beach, 2017). The importance of adult education is particularly influenced by the opportunities digital technology has provided over the last few decades. Adults can cope with a variety of learning opportunities for professional and personal growth opportunities throughout their lives (Boeren, 2017).

Various definitions of adult education explain this term in a broader context, and Andragogy needs to arise from the unique personal experience that adults have with the desire to self-determine, learn and grow. It is added that it is based on the assumption that there is sex, made during their development, and the understanding of this definition is based on "the case as a kind of phenomenon that occurs in a limited context" (Yazan, 2015). Adult education is also defined as education for both male and female adults aimed at meeting different requirements and interests based on a person's level of competence and understanding (Coles, 1969). Theories include programs to improve knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are formal or casual at learning institutions through every day or professional experience. In adult education theory, continuous learning is defined as andragogy. Scientists can also define continuous learning as a procedure of continuous education and improvement in the context of an organization and consider it as a subset of the lifelong learning process (Jain & Martindale, 2012). Knowles (1980) found that continuous learning is associated not only with the educational process at school, but also with learning that takes place throughout life. In term, adult education refers to the arts and sciences that help adults learn. In addition, Knowles (1980) defined as the process by which individuals no longer attend school and in its place participate in casual learning activities to improve their knowledge, skills and abilities.

Theories of Learning: Pedagogy and Andragogy.

In higher education, students are adult learners. Adults and children basically require the same learning conditions, and it is often said that the skills of a really good elementary school teacher can be transferred very well to working with adults. However, for adults, there are some additional things that can be useful. Malcolm Knowles' theory of adult learning is what he called "Andragogy" and adults learned it when they understood the relevance of adult education in their own circumstances (Knowles, 1984). Adult learners also learn more aggressively if they find the topic interesting. Pedagogy and Andragogy are two learning theories. In pedagogy, students need to rely on teachers for their knowledge, and what they experience can be of little value.

Andragogy, on the other hand, is a learner-focused theory that continues to be discussed as a pioneer in adult education.

Pedagogy

Pedagogy is a traditional teaching method and also means "art and science teaching children" (Knowles, 2005). Scholars aimed to develop this theory in the 7th century and teach it to children (Knowles, 2005). It is based on a set of principles that "put the teacher responsible for making all decisions about what to learn, how to learn, when to learn, and whether it has been learned" (Knowles, 2005). One of the premise of pedagogy is that learners rely on teachers to decide what information to learn when and how. The learner's experience is of little value, and the main teaching methods are lectures, assigned reading materials, and presentations (Taylor & Kroth, 2009). This teaching method works for young children, but applying educational theory to adults may not be very effective. Adult learners are partially different from child learners because they have more life experience and must be considered competent (Knowles, 2005). Therefore, education for adults needs to shift from an educational and teacher-centric focus to an andragogy and learner-centric focus to meet the needs of adult learners.

Andragogy

The advent of technology has had a major impact on education, forcing teachers to change the way adults are trained (Horsley, 2010). At the same time, adult learners needed to switch from passive learners to participation in active learning (Turcsanyi Szabo, 2012). This role change (from teacher to moderator) is the reason why teachers are encouraged to apply Andragogy's assumptions to the adult education environment. Andragogy focuses on adults and is based on six assumptions (Knowles et al., 2005): "The need to know why they have to learn something, the learner's self-concept, previously Experience, learning motivation, learning direction and motivation. These assumptions also apply to adult learners because they provide a "solid foundation for planning an adult learning experience" (Knowles, 2005). Instructors who understand and are willing to apply Andragogy's assumptions are more likely to meet the needs of adult learners, especially while education in an online environment (Cochran, 2015).

Andragogy based on the integration of two diverse and opposite traditions which are the humanistic and social traditions that advances a theory of adult learning where education is generally learner-centered. The work of Andragogy also gained its status as claiming the current status as "the art and science of helping adults learn" which is inclined by Eduard Lindeman's work in the mid 1960's which contrasted pedagogy with andragogy (Knowles, 1986). Knowles (1986) explained through the extensive research of Andragogy was that the realization of this principle is to wean adult learners off the "dependency on teaching for learning" which was encouraged traditionally by the pedagogical teaching procedure and that most teachers too, still are unaware of how adults learn. Furthermore, andragogy emphasizes the "problem-centred approach" where a likeness exists between the sphere of the educator and the learner, which similarly, describes a more collaborative learning of shifting the emphasis from the educator to the learner (Kapur, 2015).

Variances between Pedagogy and Andragogy

After the emergence of andragogy under the umbrella of adult learning, adult education theory was also formed based on pedagogy in learning theory and variations and comparisons of Andragogy. ShihkaKapur (2015) explains that adult learning (Andragogy) is continuous, as opposed to parenting (pedagogy). In contrast, pedagogy is an educational theory, andragogy is a learning theory which corresponds to conceptual education (Kapur, 2015). Education expressed in the sense of "teacher and student" and is an education from the upper and lower approaches leading to the term pedagogy and andragogy replaces the role of teacher with an intermediary. Jarvis (1985) believed, "For Education Knowles," education from above "(teachers and students) is pedagogy, and" education of equality "identified as mediators and learners is andragogy.

Knowles (1985) evaluates andragogy as a new technology that enables the improvement and application of adult education activities, especially as a theory for adult education (Kapur, 2015). The relevance of andragogy and pedagogy to theory formation is as a combination of multidimensional sets of variables including control positions, learner characteristics and situational existence conditions, central focus, dependencies, experiences, content, groups and structures (Kapur, 2015). In general, pedagogy has a more traditional structure, but andragogy offers a more flexible structure because learners are more active than those who take an educational approach. Importantly, the difference among pedagogy and andragogy is also the numerous andragogy assumptions and applications that lead to the formation of the theory itself.

Construction of Adult Learning Theory: Development of Andragogy

The formation of the adult learning theory in the late 17th century; revised and developed in the early 20th century. It defines that repetition enhances individual learning (Taylor & Hamdy, 2013). Skinner (1954) found that in adult education, a simple stimulus response was used to ensure a proper response to the stimulus that

enhanced learning. Piaget's revealed the flow of constructivist thinking in cognitive learning. Piaget envisioned the acquisition of different types of knowledge at different stages of adolescent life (Piaget, 1952). In learning analytics, Taylor and Hamdy (2013) found that social constructionists like focused on how the learning community supports learning as well as the important idea of social constructionism in which learners learn only new things. Knowledge when linking with existing knowledge. Therefore, an example of this analysis is that through already known conversations, the learner's understanding is added to the learning process, making it easier to expand the development zone by adding information about the current context. This method also simplifies how students branch what they have learned into additional learning from existing knowledge and information. The Andragogy theory and principles of Knowles (1986) come from Humanistic Psychology and Skinners (1954), which are based on theories derived from animal learning. Therefore, the theory of adult education was formed on the basis of the understanding gained from animal learning in experiments and the closely related adult learning process in education.

Towards the end of the 20th century, the formation of adult education theory is a process in which "Andragogy" is more than "pedagogy" and adults learn differently from children and become more motivated towards adults. In some typical situations, adult learners are more responsible for their own decisions compared to children, so consider the purpose of knowing the field of study. The role of their experience plays an important role in the value of their experience, and adults learn more actively for the situation. As an adult, the situation in terms of education, career, life pressure and sense of accomplishment is different from that of children. As a result, these situations highlight one of the key concepts of how adult learning theory has been formed, the main difference between adult learners and child learners that promote learning motivation. According to David Kolb (1984), empirical learning theory is the basis of adult education, as it explains the relationship between learning as part of knowledge generation itself, as the emergence of regulation in education. From a learning perspective, empirical learning, on the one hand, has found recognition through the study of Piaget's cognitive learning process (1952) as a flow of thought in constructivism. As shown in the Kolb cycle in Figure 1 below, the central role that one's experience before enrolling in school and the experience in the learning process play in the quadrant (Kolb, 1984).

Figure 1: The Kolb Cycle (1984)

In the event of specific significance to those who follow a generally constructivist line in comparison to the original model, The Kolb Cycle (1984) focuses on the previous experience and knowledge of the individual, and the disagreement between this and the real experience that is provided as the learning prospect (Kapur 2015). These enables a learner to formulate intellectual concepts of new information obtained by highlighting the main key component of `reflection` both in and on action as a fundamental process in adult learning. Through analysing The Kolb Cycle aspects of adult learning are built into course design in the formation of the theory has a significant difference than Knowles's (1985). Assumptions of Adult Learners as a premise in the four areas of self-concept, experience and orientation to learning as a development to his principles. Meanwhile, Kolb (1984) proposes a more abstract approach in which he defined that learners learn in four stages of cycle, comprising of phases of concrete experience, observation and reflection, forming abstract concepts, and testing in new situations. rather than a premise.

Principles of Adult Learning Theory

Clawson (2008) agrees the principles outlined by Knowles (1985) pioneer the field of adult education and are strong supporters of the notion that adult learners do not learn like children. Based on existing "interests" and

knowledge, adult learners learn faster when relevant to their current living conditions. Knowles is very active in promoting these principles for adult education, and andragogy principles are the opposite of those that apply to most school systems method (Knowles, 1985). Knowles (1980) found that continuous learning is not only related to the learning process at school, but also to lifelong learning. In term, adult education refers to the arts and sciences that help adults learn. Knowles (1980) found that continuous learning is not only related to the learning process at school, but also to lifelong learning. In term, adult education refers to the arts and sciences that help adults learn. In addition, according to Knowles (1980), adult education is defined as the process by which individuals no longer attend school and instead participate in informal learning activities to improve their knowledge, skills and abilities.

Adult education is one of the liberal areas of education. In addition to improving their academic qualifications, it allows adults to improve and expand their knowledge and skills. Jain and Martindale (2012) argued that continuous learning is not limited to working group members, but is important for the short-term and long-term success of individuals and organizations. Instead, it reaches people from all walks of life. It includes programs to improve knowledge, skills and attitudes. These programs can be conducted formally at an educational institution or informally through routine or professional experience. Adult learners are essentially independent and have specific goals, problem solvers, and extensive experience. Kuhn and Pease (2006) argued that adults can learn more effectively because they have a larger knowledge base to apply their knowledge, so they can learn faster. In most cases, adult learners have gone through a process of life that gives them the experience of acting as a learning resource. With increasing social responsibility, adult learners are also ready to improve their education standards. In addition, their learning orientation changes with age, shifting from subject-based learning to problem-oriented learning.

According to Clawson (2008), adult education programs benefit from the experience of participants, and these principles of adapting to the age limits of participants and adult learners challenge to encourage and enhance advanced self-development. It is suggested that there should ultimately be other principles of adult education that focus on the individual learning needs of adults. Cross (1981) added principles to make learning content courses relevant and consistent, and to create and provide a supportive and open learning environment for adults to support learning. This is because adults learn at different speeds through different teaching and training methods. Since the learning rate varies from adult to adult, the progress from "known to unknown", "simple to complex", and "concrete to abstract" described in experiential learning is very important for the sociocultural background. The learner's role in designing a framework for maintaining education among adult learners. In addition, Shihka (2015) recognized that there are several other learning principles that can be incorporated into adult learning theories to develop frameworks.

Experiential Learning Theory

David Kolb (1984) believes that experimental learning theory is a radically different view of the learning process from the behavioural theory of learning and is based on empirical epistemology. The emergence of behaviour, the relationship between learning and work, the creation of knowledge itself. Empirical learning in adult education theory was based on the intellectual origins of Dewey Ruen and Piaget's work. Their results state that adult education has features that help define the nature of experiential learning. David Kolb (1984) emphasizes that the implications and hypotheses that guide the creation of new experiences are based on two main aspects: the concrete experience and the feedback process based on the Lewin experiential learning model shown in Figure 2. increase.

Figure 2: The Lewinian experiential learning model according to Kolb (1984: 21).

Taylor and Hamdy (2013) will be able to combine these observations with David Kolb's experiential learning model (Kolb, 1985) Figure 2 to study learning and teaching strategies for adult learners. In Kolb's plan, the learner has a concrete experience that can be reflected and through that reflection can formulate abstract concepts and make appropriate generalizations. The integration of their understanding is tested by the implications of their knowledge in new situations. Levin's experiential learning model begins with a concrete experience and continues the cycle. In Kolb's terminology, "activists" feel and act, "reflectors" feel and observe, "theorists" observe and think, and "practicalists" think and act. From the educator's point of view, it is important to follow the cycle and design learning activities that can include each quadrant. However, Vella (2002) argues that the inventory of learning styles developed from the Colve cycle, while often said to be easy to understand, is unreliable and unreasonable. This is resolved due to the discord between this and the particular experience offered as a learning opportunity. The situation of this phenomenon becomes clear by seeing and observing something in the lecture. We learners take in new data for information processing from existing data. In addition, it allows you to formulate abstract concepts that give meaning to new data. When testing our knowledge, we formulate the information gained in the learning process, which ends with a consideration of our behavior.

Transformative Learning Theory

A transformative approach to learning presupposes meaningful learning when new and existing information is combined. The theory describes how individuals apply critical self-reflection throughout their development, experience as learning that transforms problematic frames of reference to make them more inclusive, discerning, reflective, open, and emotionally able to adjust (Mezirow, 2009). Kolb's Experiential Learning theory, which also emphasizes a developmental process, values reflection, and encourages active involvement of the learner as they integrate new knowledge and find meaning. (Mezirow, 2000). It continues to say that it is important to link new knowledge with what is already known, but the link is more accurate than the general one (Stein, 1984). Sophistication is the sorting and sorting of information to get meaningful elements. Finally, under restructuring, you will understand the development of new knowledge maps (schemes) that will allow you to become an expert and prove your expertise. This idea is similar to Malcolm Knowles' Andragogy approach, but refines David Kolb's theory of adult education in a more comprehensive way in the relationship between inclusiveness and generational guided behavior.

Figure 3: Transformative Learning

Capabilities emphasized by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) include a combination of knowledge, skills and actions practiced for self-improvement. Similarly, Salleh (2012) describes abilities as a set of skills, knowledge, and behaviours that characterize better performance in all aspects of a person. Ability is based on the values of life, the individual's attitude and inner motivation to complete the task at hand and do a good job. According to Rychen and Salganik (2001), abilities are not limited to knowledge and skills. Rather, it is about the ability to meet complex requirements by providing psychosocial resources such as skills and attitudes in specific situations. Each organization has a different concept of competence

Adult Learning Theory Application in Higher Education

Adults need to know the purpose of the learning process before they can begin it (Knowles, 2005). By explaining the purpose of the task and the learning outcomes of the task before assigning the task, adult learners can increase their chances of motivating them to complete the task. Adult students are more likely to be motivated when they understand what they should learn. Tasks that connect learners to life experiences make activities in the classroom more relevant, thereby actively engaging students in learning. The literature presented to learners through real case studies can be an effective learning method, especially in online learning environments (Conlan, Grabowski & Smith, 2011).

According to Dabbagh (2007) online learner self-concept is an important predictor of success, and students with internal control points tend to be more successful in an online learning environment. Online teachers should be willing to give up control of the course so that learners can work on the content of the course on an equal footing with the teacher (Conrad & Donaldson, 2004). Activities that support and encourage online learners in this area must be collaborative (Dabbagh, 2007). Adults must be considered competent (Knowles, 2005), and shared activities provide adults with the opportunity to demonstrate their skills.

Encouraging learners to combine their learning with life experiences helps them better understand the material (Whitewater, 2006). Students who actively participate and contribute to learning are more motivated and motivated to learn (Harper & Ross, 2011) and are therefore more successful. Teachers need to create a learning environment that encourages and encourages learners to share their personal experiences, ideas, and opinions (Palloff & Pratt, 2001). Useful activities such as sharing past experiences include contemplating the journal by sharing the learner's knowledge on a particular topic and writing short exercises to contemplate (Aragon, 2003). This may include adult experience as an effective assessment tool for sharing previous experience and a fulfilling learning environment (Whitewater, 2006).

Learner's willingness to learn. This means aligning learning with the notion of development (Knowles et al., 2005). To ensure the success of online learners, the needs of learners need to be addressed quickly (Blondy, 2007). By using an asynchronous environment, instructors can use discussion questions to facilitate engagement with fellow students. In an asynchronous environment, students have time to ponder what others are saying and organize their thoughts before responding. Student answers help the instructor better understand the learner's willingness to learn the content of the course and give them a better understanding of what they are about to learn. The learner's learning direction is that adult learners are motivated to learn when given real learning activities (Knowles, 2005). According to specific needs "(Blondy, 2007). It is very important for the success of students that teachers attract the attention of adults and provide activities that keep them attracted (Conrad & Donaldson, 2004). Genuine learning activities provide "meaning beyond the learning environment" (Conrad & Donaldson, 2004). Examples of real activities are case studies, team problem-solving activities, and interviews (Conrad & Donaldson, 2004).

Learner motivation is that adult learners are inherently motivated to learn (Knowles et al., 2005). Teachers can support students' motivation to learn by providing a learning environment that includes: Attract students and encourage them to participate actively (Aragon, 2003). Teachers need to recognize the need for learners to create a positive adult learning environment in an online environment as it should be cherished and respected (Blondy, 2007). Using games in an online environment, simulating a radio talk show to involve guests, and using multimedia as needed are all successfully used to increase student motivation (Aragon, 2003). One of the benefits of using Andragogy is the ability to adapt assumptions to the needs and learning situations of individual learners. Teaching adult learners can be difficult, especially in an online learning environment. For example, in online education, teachers need to use different skills than face-to-face education (Hoekstra, 2014). Educators who understand Andragogy's assumptions and can effectively apply them in an online environment may be more successful in a virtual environment, so learners can be more successful (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011).

Conclusion

Educators who are using adult education concepts in the development of their lessons must also become facilitators of learning. Andragogy is an adult learning theory that can be applied to various learning environments, and is particularly valuable when utilized in online learning. Teachers who understand Andragogy may find it easier to teach in an online educational environment. Understanding how adults learn and implement the assumptions of Andragogy theory helps teachers provide online learners with the support and guidance they need to create a more helpful environment.

References

- Al-Menayes, J. (2015). Motivations for Using Social Media: An Exploratory Factor Analysis. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*.
- Beach, P. (2017). Self-directed online learning: A theoretical model for understanding elementary teachers' online learning experiences. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 61, 60-72.
- Blondy, L. (2007). Evaluation and Application of Andragogical Assumptions to the Adult Online Learning Environment. *Journal of Interactive Online Learning*. 6.

- Boeren, E. (2017). Understanding adult lifelong learning participation as a layered problem. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 39(2), 161-175.
- Cardy, R. L., & Selvarajan, T. T. (2006). Competencies: Alternative frameworks for competitive advantage. *Business Horizons*, 49(3), 235-245.
- Clawson, H. J., & Dutch, N. (2008). *Addressing the needs of victims of human trafficking: Challenges, barriers, and promising practices*. Washington, DC: Department of Health and Human Services, Office of the Assistant Secretary for Planning and Evaluation.
- Clawson, James. (2008). *Adult Learning Theory*.
- Coles, E.T. (1969). *Adult education in developing countries*. Oxford, England: Pergamon Press.
- Hanson, A., Edwards, A., & Hanson, A. (1996). The search for a separate theory of adult learning. *Boundaries of adult learning*, 99-107.
- Henschke, J. A. (2011, September). Building blocks for the adult learning experience. In *Proceedings of the 2011 Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, Extension, and Community Education*.
- Horne, Zach & Muradoglu, Melis & Cimpian, Andrei. (2019). Explanation as a Cognitive Process. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. 23. 187-199. 10.1016.
- Illeris, K. (2010). Characteristics of adult learning. *International Encyclopedia of Education*, 36– 41.
- Jain, S., & Martindale, E. T. (2012). Facilitating continuous learning: A review of research and practice on individual learning capabilities and organizational learning environments. *the Proceedings of Association for Educational Communication & Technology (AECT)*, 288-297.
- Jain, S., & Martindale, E. T. (2012). Facilitating continuous learning: A review of research and practice on individual learning capabilities and organizational learning environments. *the Proceedings of Association for Educational Communication & Technology (AECT)*, 288-297.
- Kapur, Shikha. (2015). Andragogy: The Adult Learning Theory. *Indian Journal of Adult Education*. 76. 50-60.
- Kim, Y. S., & Merriam, S. B. (2010). Situated learning and identity development in a Korean older adults' computer classroom. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 60(5), 438-455.
- Knowles, M. S. (1970). *The Modern Practice of Adult Education; Andragogy versus Pedagogy*.
- Knowles, M. S. (1980). *From pedagogy to andragogy. Religious Education*.
- Knowles, M. S., Holton III, E. F., & Swanson, R. A. (2005). *The adult learner: The definitive classic in adult education and human resource development (6th ed.)*. San Diego, CA: Elsevier.
- Knowles, Malcolm S. and Associates. (1985) *Andragogy in Action: Applying Modern Principles of Adult Learning*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 1985; pp.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). Experience as the source of learning and development prentice-hall. *Englewood Cliffs*, 31-61.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development (Vol. 1)*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Kolb, David. (1984). *Experiential Learning: Experience as The Source of Learning and Development*.
- Kuhn, D., & Pease, M. (2006). Do children and adults learn differently? *Journal of cognition and development*, 7(3), 279-293.
- Mezirow, J. (2000). Learning to think like an adult. *Learning as transformation: Critical perspectives on a theory in progress*, 3-33.
- Mezirow, J., & Taylor, E. W. (Eds.). (2009). *Transformative learning in practice: Insights from community, workplace, and higher education*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Piaget J. (1952). *The origins of intelligence in children*. New York: International University Press
- Salleh, K. M., Khalid, N. H., Sulaiman, N. L., Mohamad, M. M., & Sern, L. C. (2015). Competency of adult learners in learning: application of the iceberg competency model. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 204, 326-334.
- Skinner B. (1954). The science of learning and the art of teaching. *Harvard Educ Rev* 24:86–9
- Stein, B. S., Littlefield, J., Bransford, J. D., & Persampieri, M. (1984). Elaboration and knowledge acquisition. *Memory & Cognition*, 12(5), 522-529.
- Taylor, D. C., & Hamdy, H. (2013). Adult learning theories: implications for learning and teaching in medical education: AMEE Guide No. 83. *Medical teacher*, 35(11), e1561-e1572.
- Taylor, David & Hamdy, Hossam. (2013). Adult learning theories: Implications for learning and teaching in medical education: AMEE Guide No. 83. *Medical teacher*. 35. 10.3109/0142159X.2013.828153.
- UNESCO, ILO (2001). *Technical and Vocational Education and Training for the twenty-first century (Technical Report)*. Retrieved from unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001260/126050e.pdf.
- Vella, J. (2002). *Learning to Listen, learning to Teach the Power of Dialogue in Educating Adults Revised Edition*.
- Yazan, B. (2015). Three approaches to case study methods in education: Yin, Merriam, and Stake. *The qualitative report*, 20(2), 134-152.

Yazan, Bedrettin. (2015). Three Approaches to Case Study Methods in Education: Yin, Merriam, and Stake. Qualitative Report. 20.

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